

MEDICINAL POTENTIAL AND BIOECOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF LAMIACEAE SPECIES IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *The Lamiaceae family, commonly known as the mint family, comprises a vast array of plant species with significant medicinal, aromatic, and ornamental value. This article explores the bioecological properties of various medicinal species within the Lamiaceae family, particularly those found in Uzbekistan. The study emphasizes the importance of these species in local and industrial applications, highlighting their roles in traditional and modern medicine, food, and perfumery industries. Data were collected from various botanical texts, research articles, and field studies conducted in different regions of Uzbekistan. The bioecological properties, traditional uses, and current applications of these species were analyzed to provide a holistic understanding of their significance. Additionally, field observations and specimen collections were conducted to verify the presence and ecological characteristics of specific species. This comprehensive review aims to provide insights into the biodiversity, ecological significance, and potential applications of these plants, underscoring the need for their conservation and sustainable utilization.*

Keywords: *lamiaceae, medicinal plants, bioecological properties, Uzbekistan flora, essential oils, conservation.*

INTRODUCTION

The mint family (Lamiaceae), one of the largest plant families in the world, is known for its rich variety and wide distribution, especially abundant in hot and temperate climates. The family Lamiaceae has more than 230 genera and more than 7,000 species [9]. The family Lamiaceae contains many plants of economic and medicinal importance. There are 238 species from 39 species in Uzbekistan, and 69 species have medicinal properties. This article will study the bioecological properties of these medicinal species, their traditional use and the possibilities of their application in modern pharmaceuticals and industry.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

The mint family (Lamiaceae) has been extensively studied due to its economic, medicinal and ecological importance [2,3,4,6]. This review covers important aspects of its biodiversity, traditional uses and modern applications. The mint family (Lamiaceae) contains more than 200 genera and about 3,000 species worldwide, which are significantly manifested in the Mediterranean, Central Asia and temperate regions [6]. 238 species of 39 species have been documented in Uzbekistan, showing high biodiversity, especially in Fergana Valley. Marmarac (Salvia L.), Mint (Mentha L.), Togjambil (Thymus L.), Deer (Zizifora L.), Limonote (Melissa L.), Maple (Leonurus L.) and Tograikhan (Origanum L.) descendants are among the most expressed and studied due to their widespread use in traditional medicine and modern pharmacology [2].

Traditional application. Historically, Mint (Lamiaceae) species have been used in various traditional medicine systems [3]. For example, the medicinal marmalade (*Salvia officinalis*) has been used in European herbal medicine for centuries for its anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties. Similarly, Peppermint (*Mentha spicata*) and Peppermint (*Mentha piperita*) have been used in both culinary and medicinal contexts for their benefits for digestion and respiration. The roots and some parts of the Baikal cocoon (*Scutellaria baicalensis*) are used in traditional Chinese medicine for their anti-inflammatory and anti-cancer properties.

In modern medicine, Mint (Lamiaceae) species remain valuable due to their richness in bioactive compounds such as essential oils, flavonoids and phenolic acids. For example, medicinal Rosemary (*Rosmarinus officinalis*) has been extensively researched for its overall potency-enhancing and anti-inflammatory effects. The common mountain hummingbird (*Thymus vulgaris*) is known for its antimicrobial and antioxidant properties, which makes it a staple in the pharmaceutical and cosmetic industries. In addition, essential oils from Lavender (*Lavandula angustifolia*) are widely used in aromatherapy to relieve stress and anxiety.

The preservation of medicinal Mint species (Lamiaceae) is especially important in the regions of Uzbekistan. Excessive harvesting and habitat loss pose a major threat to these species. Sustainable practices, including the cultivation and proper management of wild populations, are necessary to ensure their continued existence. Studies on the methods of cultivation of the main species, such as bozulbang (*L. Inebrians* Bge.) and elegant deer, chulyalpiz (*Z. tenuior* L.), have shown promising results in increasing the yield and quality of medicinal compounds.

This study focused on species common in Uzbekistan through a comprehensive review of existing literature on the mint family (Lamiaceae). The data is collected from various botanical texts, research articles and field studies conducted in different regions of Uzbekistan. The bioecological properties, traditional applications, and current applications of these species have been analyzed for a holistic understanding of their importance. In addition, field observations and specimen collections were conducted to verify the presence and ecological characteristics of specific species.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In Uzbekistan, the mint family (Lamiaceae) is represented by 238 species in 39 Generations, with a significant diversity in Fergana Valley, where 59 species from 26 genera are found. Notable lineages include the Bozulbang (*Lagochilus* Bge.), Deer (*Ziziphora tenior* L.), Marmarac (*Salvia* L.) and Bumblebee (*Dracocephalum* L.), each of which has several species with medicinal properties. Distributed mainly in warm and temperate regions, it grows in a variety of ecological niches ranging from rocky areas to wet, shady areas.

Medicinal properties and applications. Several species in the family Lamiaceae are traditionally used for their medicinal properties. For example:

- *Qatortishli* devoltegiot (*m.alternidens* Rech.): This perennial plant, known for its use in the treatment of respiratory and throat diseases, is widespread in Tashkent, Fergana, Samarkand and other regions. It is used to treat coughs, colds and other respiratory problems.

- Medicinal lemonade (*M.officinalis* L.): Commonly called medicinal lemongrass, it is used to treat digestive problems, anemia and nervous disorders. Its pleasant lemon scent also makes it popular in aromatherapy. Studies have shown that its essential oil has significant antioxidant and antiviral properties.

- Field mint, water mint (*M.arvensis* L.): field mint is widely used for its anti-nausea, digestive and calming properties. Its essential oil is a key ingredient in various medicinal preparations, especially in the treatment of acute intestinal syndrome and other gastrointestinal diseases.

- Mountain raikon (*O.tytthanthum* L.): This small-flowered mountain basil is used for its expectorant and digestive-stimulating properties, often included in the treatment of respiratory diseases. It has also been studied for its antimicrobial activity, especially against pathogens of the respiratory tract.

- Drunk bozulbang (*L.Inebrians* Bunge.): Applied to stop bleeding and promote wound healing, this species is characterized by its hemostatic properties. Research shows that its extracts have a significant wound healing and anti-inflammatory effect.

- Turkestan arslonquyruği (*L.turkestanicus* V. I.Krecz. & Kuprian.). In folk medicine, water-alcohol extract and tincture are used as sedatives in the treatment of heart disease.

Species	Popularly known as	Healing properties	Application
<i>Marrubium alternidens</i>	<i>Qatortishli devoltegiot</i>	In the treatment of respiratory diseases	Cough, colds, breathing problems
<i>Melissa officinalis</i>	<i>Dorivor limono't</i>	In the treatment of digestive problems, nervous disorders	Aromatherapy, antioxidant
<i>Mentha arvensis</i>	<i>Dala yalpizi</i>	Against nausea, in improving digestion	Treatment of acute intestinal syndrome, gastrointestinal problems
<i>Origanum tytthanthum</i>	<i>Tog' rayhon</i>	When moving sputum, improving digestion	In respiratory diseases, antimicrobial
<i>Lagochilus hirsutissimus</i>	<i>Tikanli bozulbang</i>	In the treatment of wounds, anti-inflammatory	When stopping bleeding, when finishing wounds
<i>Betonica betoniciflora</i>	<i>Tog'quddusi</i>	At the time of pregnancy, childbirth	In gynecological diseases
<i>Zizifora</i>	<i>Kiyiko't</i>	Appetite, normalization of blood pressure	In cardiovascular disease

The bioecological properties of mint (*Lamiaceae*) species differ significantly. For example, Devoltegiot (*M.alternidens* Rech.) grows on roadsides, under walls, and on abandoned land. Medicinal lemonade (*M. officinalis* L.) prefers shallow, shaded areas. These species exhibit a variety of morphological characters, such as those of the medicinal lemonade (*M.officinalis* L.) of an erect, branching stem or intoxicating bozulbang (*L.Inebrians* Bunge.) while the leaves are rhombic-ovoid. Understanding these characteristics is critical to developing conservation strategies and optimizing their use in various fields.

Protection and sustainable use. The increased demand for medicinal plants requires an effective storage strategy. It is critical to identify important habitats and develop sustainable

harvesting methods to prevent natural populations from declining. In addition, the cultivation of medicinal species in a controlled environment helps to meet industrial demand while maintaining wild populations. The study of the bioecological properties of these plants can provide information on breeding programs and the development of high-quality raw materials for use in pharmaceutical purposes.

Species of mint (Lamiaceae) are important in various areas. Essential oils from species such as lavender (*Lavandula angustifolia*) and medicinal Rosemary (*Rosmarinus officinalis*) are highly valued in the perfumery and cosmetic industries for their aroma and therapeutic properties. In addition, the use of Mountain Amber (*Thymus vulgaris*) and Mountain basil (*Origanum vulgare*) for culinary purposes underlines the importance of the family in the food industry, providing taste and preserving properties due to their antimicrobial properties.

Conclusion

The mint family (Lamiaceae) represents a rich resource of medicinal and economically valuable plants. In Uzbekistan, these species occupy an important place in folk medicine and have opportunities for application in industry. Conservation efforts and sustainable use practices are important to ensure the continued use of these valuable resources. Future research should focus on studying all the possibilities of Mint (Lamiaceae) species, including their pharmacological properties and their application in modern medicine.

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